

Design of a Programmable Rainfall Simulator

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Abstract

A programmable controller (PIC) was designed to provide a greater flexibility in rainfall simulator research. The PIC controlled the rainfall simulator using a process control board employing a microprocessor. This control board provided programmable capability previously unavailable in field research. Software to control the system was developed using assembly language and a microprocessor emulator. This software provided user-friendly interaction and the ability for variations in rainfall intensity and storm duration in simulated rainfall studies.

Introduction

Rainfall simulators are used to study hydrologic process such as infiltration, erosion, sediment transport, and runoff. Although less known, simulated rainfall has also been used to study water quality processes such as the washoff of foliar applied pesticides, nutrient - sediment equilibria, and nutrient leaching from crop residues. As rainfall simulators provide control of natural environmental factors such as rainfall intensity and duration, they are used to determine basic information on these hydrologic and chemical processes [1].

Most rainfall simulators utilize oscillating nozzles to provide the necessary raindrop size and intensities to simulate natural rainfall. The sweeping action of the nozzles is controlled by a timer that provides only a single constant time delay, and hence a single rainfall intensity, for each oscillation. However, natural rainfall does not occur at a constant rate.

Studies have shown that runoff and erosion are greatly affected by the storm intensity and that simulated uniform storms do not produce runoff and erosion rates of natural occurring storms [2] as natural storm events are seldom of one intensity. Thus, a programmable controller was designed to control variations in storm

intensity and duration of a storm event. While microcomputers could be implemented in controlling simulations [3], they would require added peripheral devices and could not withstand adverse environmental conditions experienced in field studies. For these reasons, the PIC was designed using a microprocessor process control board which provided the required programmable capability and user friendly operation. This instrument was then assembled in a environmentally sealed case for protection against the elements. This paper describes the hardware and software development of the design.

Hardware design

The PIC was designed to control the oscillating nozzle simulator of Meyer and Harmon [4], depicted in Figure 1, which produces drop size and impact velocity similar to natural rainfall over a 1 m² plot. The sweeping motion of the nozzles between two troughs at 3.05 m above the soil surface produces the simulated rainfall on the plot at the desired rainfall intensity. The troughs return excess water to a reservoir for reuse. Rainfall intensity is controlled by governing the delay time between sweeps using a motor/clutch pair (Fig. 2). The motor constantly rotates at 60 rpm and is engaged to the nozzle linkage when a 24 VDC pulse is applied to the clutch.

Figure 1. Rainfall Simulator utilizing oscillating nozzles

Figure 2. Motor/Clutch Assembly

To control the clutch pulse, and hence the storm intensity, a prefabricated control board using an 8 bit microprocessor was chosen for the design. This board operated off of 120 VAC and provided 40K of EPROM, display and keypad connections, real-time clock (battery powered), and four I/O ports for peripheral devices. The user is provided I/O capabilities from an environmentally sealed keypad and an 8 line by 40 character LCD which are connected to JP3 and JP1, respectively. To provide the required voltage for the clutch of 24 VDC @ 1.25 A, a dc power converter was used. A circuit layout and a description of major components is given in Figure 3.

A micro switch (Fig. 4) and relay circuit (Fig. 5) respectively, furnish the 24 V pulse required to engage the clutch. The control board provides a 5 VDC step from port PD2 to the input transistor, and hence saturates the transistor, turning the relay on. To prevent transient spikes upon actuation, a 28 V zener diode and a 1µF capacitor parallel combination were used on both input and output contacts of the relay. Once the motor/clutch is engaged, the nozzle linkage (Fig. 1) rotates 180° until the micro switch falls into the slotted cam. Port D0 monitors the micro switch during the rotation waiting for the switch to fall (Fig. 5) which is discussed later as a software application. When the fall was detected, by a high PD0, the 5 V step was removed from the relay circuit creating the required clutch pulse. This procedure allows the software to control the delay time, and hence the rainfall intensity, to create the desired simulated rainfall event.

Software design

Assembly language was used to develop the software used by the microprocessor. The assembled code was "burned" into an 8K EPROM chip. Elimination of trial and error "burning" of the EPROM during development

was accomplished by using a microprocessor emulator. The emulator operated from a personal computer which allowed easy access to the board during testing and proved to be an invaluable tool for programming.

Figure 3 Circuit Layout of PIC

User friendly operation of the PIC was a major concern in the software development. For this reason, the program was based on menu driven instructions. On power-up of the system, the menu appears on the LCD. Option 1 instructs the user to input a constant delay time for oscillation. The resolution of the time delay is .01 seconds. The simulator operation will begin after the entry of delay time and depressing the start button. The simulator operation can be terminated at any time during the simulation by depressing a "1" on the keypad. Option 2 prompts the user as above in option 1, but with an added feature of duration of the storm event. The simulator begins operation upon entry and will automatically shut off at the end of the entered duration time. Starting and terminating the simulation is also performed as in Option 1. While Option 1 and 2 provide a uniform intensity, Option 3 creates three stepped increases and/or decreases in rainfall intensity and duration during a single storm event. Option 3 instructs the user to input three delay times and corresponding duration times. When the start button is depressed, operation will proceed with the delay times changing automatically upon the expiration of their respective duration time. Operation can also be terminated at any time by depressing "1". During any of the options, the cycles of oscillation are updated and displayed on the LCD. At the end of simulation the program returns to the menu of option listings. Option 4 lets the user observe the total cycles after a completion of the storm event.

The program is a set of subroutines which are given in Table 1. The subroutine GETTIME produces the 5

VDC output needed to excite the relay. GETTIME waits on the time delay, which is provided by the calling program, to expire and then places a high (5 V) out of port D2. GETTIME then monitors the micro switch circuit (PD0) for a 5 V signal (micro switch normally open) and subsequently outputs a low (0 V) out on port D2 which produces a signal oscillation. Once the pulse has been executed, the program counter returns to the calling subroutine. With this subroutine and others listed in Table 1, any option of storm intensity and duration can be developed to acquire the needed storm pattern. The software described was developed for testing purposes of the PIC. Further programming will be required to meet the scientist preferences on storm simulation. The final product proved to be very user friendly and provided a useful instrument in rainfall simulation studies.

Figure 4. Schematic of Micro switch Circuit

Figure 5. Schematic for Relay Circuit

Table 1. Subroutines used for program development.

Name	Description
MAIN	Displays the main menu and waits for user entry
CONST	Displays screen for Option 1 and waits on user entry of time delay
GETTIME	Performs the time delay and outputs 5 VDC on PD2 and monitors PD0
COUNT	Counts the number of oscillations (up to 99,999)
DCONST	Displays screen for option 2 and waits for user entry of time delay and duration
STEP	Displays screen for option 3 and waits on user entries of the time delays and corresponding durations
DSPCYC	Displays screen for Option 4 which outputs the total oscillations
KEYIN	Retrieves user entries from keyboard and echoes to LCD
DISP	Displays memory of address "disptype"

Summary

The programmable intensity controller utilized a microprocessor control board to provide constant and variable storm intensities during a rainfall simulation which met the requirements of the design proposal. It also has expandable features, such as memory and I/O capabilities, which will allow future improvements without redesigning the system. The added feature of varying rainfall intensities will give scientist flexibility in studies of environmental factors associated with rainfall.

References

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